

Research on the habits of Erasmus students:

consumer, daily life, and travel
habits of Erasmus students from the
perspective of their environmental
attitudes and beliefs

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Editors:

Anya Diekmann, Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB)
Georgios Karaiskos, Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB)

Contributors:

All project partners

Design:

Lemonia Moraiti

Photos & Illustrations:

Unsplash
Vecteezy

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Erasmus Student Network
European Students' Union
European University Foundation
Students Organising for Sustainability UK
Technische Hochschule Köln
Université Libre de Bruxelles

Contact:

www.greenerasmus.org

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The background features a dark green upper section and a lighter green lower section, separated by a white diagonal line. Faint, overlapping white lines create a geometric pattern across the entire page. The word 'INTRODUCTION' is centered in a bold, white, sans-serif font with a slight drop shadow.

INTRODUCTION

The last few decades have witnessed a significant growth in student mobility across countries for the purpose of studying. This kind of mobility is part of a new type of tourism, known as “Academic Tourism”, which includes any stays made in higher education institutions in places outside the students’ usual environment for a period of less than one year (Rodriguez et al, 2013:89).

Literature so far has given substantial attention to international student mobility in higher education (economics, cultural exchange, education etc.) however little consideration has been given to its environmental impact or sustainability (Shields, 2019:596). Student mobility, while less studied, also contributes to universities’ environmental footprint (Arsenault et al, 2019:1). There are numerous studies on the integration of sustainability issues in “higher education institutions” (HEIs) (particularly in the US) with a significant number of studies looking into the external determinants of sustainability behaviours in general (and within HEIs) but despite those research developments, little focus on the students’ perspectives and consumption patterns of students on mobility has been made. As Shields (2019) points out, much literature discusses higher education as an agent for sustainable development, but the extent to which higher education contributes to unsustainable economic and social systems receives less attention.

The link between international student mobility and global climate change constitutes an important gap in the literature (Shields, 2019:596). Although it’s proven that higher education could play an important role in shaping future sustainability attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours and contribute to an increase in environmental literacy (Whitley et al, 245), little research has been done so far on how those socio-psychological factors impact the environmental behaviour of students and the degree to which they explain the attitude-behaviour gap in students’

environmental behaviour.

Having identified this gap in existing research, the current study aims to look deeper into the aspects related to the ecological footprint of students’ mobility. The research therefore aims to:

- **map students’ behaviours and consumption patterns at home and during mobility**
- **explore the reasons behind student’s behaviour**
- **examine the extent to which socio-psychological factors such as beliefs, attitudes and norms impact students’ consumption and behaviour.**

As the mapping is one of the key features of the research, a quantitative survey was disseminated in spring 2021 resulting in over 10.000 valid responses from all over Europe.

This report is divided into several sections:

After a short **literature review** and an **introduction** to various theories related to environmental behaviour, the **methodology** of the research is explained. This is followed by **a critical analysis of some selected results** looking into the links between behaviour, attitudes, and beliefs.

The survey questions can be found in Annex I, and the detailed data from the survey in Annex II.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To understand the reasoning behind the research, it is important to explore the theoretical background.

The sustainability of international higher education: student mobility and global climate change

As already highlighted, the global climate crisis places higher education institutions and systems in a challenging position. On the one hand, various efforts, though still limited, have been undertaken to match research with the scientific requirements of sustainable development (Waas et al., 2009:634) and lead to the production of knowledge and technology with the potential to transform economic activities towards greater efficiency and lower environmental impact (Shields, 2019: 594). On the other hand, higher education institutions themselves are embedded in an economy that is heavily reliant on carbon-based energy that produces greenhouse gases (GHG), the root cause of the global climate change crisis (Shields, 2019:594).

Undoubtedly a fair amount of a university's ecological footprint is intricately linked with actions related to academic mobility. When focusing on the ecological footprint of academic mobility, and more specifically when focusing on the ecological footprint of the Erasmus mobility scheme, there are two main categories that should be considered: consumption patterns and travel patterns.

Travel patterns

Data from recent studies provide some insight into the travel behaviour of Erasmus students. The majority of Erasmus students travel out of their current country of residence (81.7%) while on mobility. They mostly travel to neighbouring countries (Durovic, Lovrentej, 2015:5). Holidays are shorter in comparison with those done while at home, and one-day tour visits have increased (Durovic, Lovrentej, 2015:5).

Travel is closely related to students' ecological footprint. The part of the ecological footprint that is associated with mobility (of both humans and goods) comes mostly from the amount of CO₂ produced by the means of travel (car, plane etc.) (Borzsak et al, 2019:123). However, the mobility part of the footprint depends on how much a person travels and by what means. The most common means of transport in order of increasing footprints are on foot – by bicycle – by public transport – by car – by plane. (Borzsak et al, 2019:124). The vast majority of international students are likely to travel through international aviation, as planes account for the overwhelming majority of international transportation (Shields, 2019:596).

Consumption patterns

The four main areas of behaviour that affect one's individual carbon footprint are nutrition, housing, mobility, and consumption, such as clothing, appliances, furniture, electronic devices, paper, etc. (Borzsak et al, 2019:124). There are several factors in each category that have a major impact on the individual footprint. The size (and proportion) of these categories varies from country to country based on the industrialisation, habits, lifestyle, climate, and natural resources of the country (Borzsak et al, 2019:124). **Unlike travel-related emissions, changes in consumption emissions can also be positive, as it is possible that students produce less GHG¹ in the host country than they would have at home** (Shields, 2019:597).

¹ GHG: Greenhouse gas, any gas that has the property of absorbing infrared radiation (net heat energy) emitted from Earth's surface and reradiating it back to Earth's surface, thus contributing to the greenhouse effect. Carbon dioxide, methane, and water vapour are the most important greenhouse gases. (source: britannica.com)

The attitude-behaviour gap in students' environmental behaviour

Attitude towards a behaviour refers to “the degree to which a person has a favourable or unfavourable evaluation or appraisal of the behaviour in question” (Ajzen, 1991, p. 188). Although research assumes that attitude towards a behaviour positively affects behavioural intention (Han, 2015, p. 167), **little is known about how individual values and beliefs influence behaviours or the intentions to engage in sustainable behaviours**’ (Whitley et al, 2018: 247).

Research in the field of tourism shows that tourists care about the environment and do not wish to harm it. Yet the very fact that they go on vacation often has negative environmental consequences (Juvan, Dolnicar, 2014:91). This highlights the fact that **there is a certain attitude-behaviour gap. Indeed, several authors have shown that ecological concern is not necessarily translated into more sustainable practices** (Chuvienco et al, 2018:1373). Juvan and Dolnicar (2014) explain that study participants generally admitted to feeling a tension between their attitudes towards the environment and its protection, and their vacation behaviour.

Factors associated with more pro-environmental attitudes and behaviours are still poorly understood. In the past few decades, several review papers have identified factors linked to environmental concern, but their conclusions often vary (Chuvienco et al, 2018:1372-1373). Several theoretical models have been developed, in an attempt to investigate the factors that cause or hinder engagement in a certain behaviour. These will be presented and discussed in the next section.

Exploring the attitude-behaviour relationship: theoretical models

Key theories for explaining the environmental behaviour of an individual include the (I) Knowledge Deficit Model, the (II) Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and the (III) Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) Theory. The last two models were selected for their ability to explore a variety of socio-psychological factors such as attitudes and beliefs that can help explain students' behaviour. Among them, VBN has the added value of considering norms when analysing human behaviour, recognising the influence that standard patterns of acceptable behaviour can have in the development of certain behaviours. Finally, the Knowledge Deficit Model, although obsolete for some (Heeren et al., 2016), provided a valuable insight on the role of information and awareness in the development of certain behaviours.

Values

Values are abstract ideas, such as sustainability and equality, which contribute to our decision-making capabilities, framing our attitudes and leading us to engage in associated behaviours. More specifically, 'values are thought to be (a) concepts or beliefs, (b) about desirable end states or behaviours, (c) that transcend specific states, (d) guide selection or evaluation of behaviour and events, and (e) are ordered by relative importance' (Schwartz, Bilsky, 1987:551).

Biospheric Values

Biospheric value orientation indicates "values emphasizing the environment and the biosphere itself" (De Groot et al., 2007:104).

Attitudes

Attitude toward the behaviour refers to "the degree to which a person has a favourable or unfavourable evaluation or appraisal of the behaviour in question" (Ajzen, 1991:188).

Beliefs

Beliefs are judgments about ourselves and the world around us (Whitley et al, 2016:248).

Norms

Norms are standard patterns of acceptable behaviour. The assumption is that norms influence behaviour and decision-making processes is reminiscent of Schwartz's norm activation theory (Whitley et al, 2016:249).

Social Norms

Social Norms (or subjective norms), perceived social pressure to perform or not perform a behaviour (Ajzen, 1991:188).

PBC (Perceived Behaviour Control)

PBC examines whether an individual believes it is possible to engage in the behaviour (Heeren et al, 2016:617). If there are barriers influencing the likelihood a person will exhibit a behaviour, whether actual or perceived barriers, the model hypothesizes that it is unlikely that an individual will intend to engage in the behaviour (Heeren et al, 2016:617).

Figure 1 - Definitions of used terms.

The Knowledge Deficit Model

The traditional **“Knowledge Deficit Model”** places **knowledge as the key component determining whether an individual behaves in a certain way or adopts a certain behaviour** (Heeren et al, 2016:616). By this rationale, the solution to a problem is simply communicating better information to the appropriate audience to change behaviour. A common misperception is that unsustainable behaviours are largely driven by a lack of knowledge of the underlying societal costs and the contributing factors leading to environmental degradation. Such a perception assumes if individuals “only knew better” they would engage in more sustainable behaviours (Heeren et al, 2016:613).

Although the assumption that knowledge guides behaviour has significantly influenced curricula and education programmes, this assumption has been heavily criticised, particularly among social psychologists that point to other cognitive factors that may be better predictors of behaviour (Heeren et al, 2016:614). Specifically, the “Knowledge Deficit Model” is criticised for not incorporating psychological research about how knowledge relates to behaviour (Heeren et al, 2016:614). It also entails an implicit assumption that knowing more science will lead to greater public support or appreciation for science. As research has indicated this certainly cannot be relied upon, with greater knowledge about science sometimes leading to greater scepticism of it (Irwin, Wayne, 1996:154). Sustainability knowledge is important to guide decision-making but is insufficient by itself to change behaviour.

Figure 2 - The Knowledge Deficit Model.

Sustainability knowledge is important to guide decision-making but is insufficient by itself to change behaviour. Social psychologists suggest that a sequence of factors such as values, beliefs, and norms play an important role in motivating pro-environmental behaviours (Dietz, Fitzgerald, and Shwom 2005). Some values, beliefs, and norms may also diminish environmental attitudes and have negative impacts on associated behaviours (Dietz, Fitzgerald, and Shwom 2005). That is where the next two models come in to cover this ground and respond to the gaps of the Knowledge Deficit Model.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

Ajzen et al. (2011) performed a series of studies examining the role knowledge plays in predicting behaviour. Studies on energy conservation predicted that general knowledge of an issue, such as conservation and sustainability, would not be a significant predictor of behaviour. Knowledge explained less than 1% of the variance in energy saving behaviour. Attitudes, norms and perceived behaviour control were stronger predictors of behavioural intentions and behaviour.

The “**Theory of Planned Behaviour**” is one of the most utilised theories to explain the factors leading individuals to engage in behaviour. It **posits that three variables predict behavioural intentions: attitudes towards the behaviour, social norms regarding the behaviour, and perceived behaviour control** (Heeren et al, 2016:617). TPB postulates that attitudes, social norms and perceived behavioural control affect people’s intentions to behave in certain ways which, in turn, lead to actual behaviour (Jucvan, Dolnicar, 2014:77) and has frequently been used as a basis for investigating environmentally sustainable behaviour in general (Jucvan, Dolnicar, 2014:77). In a nutshell, the theory suggests that whether an individual actually engages in the behaviour is a result of their intentions and whether the individual perceives the behaviour as possible (Heeren et al, 2016:617).

The Value-Belief-Norm Theory

The VBN framework is formulated on value frameworks and has received substantial recognition in recent times. An **added value of the VBN theory**, in comparison with the TPB theory, **is that it considers the values.**

VBN begins with value orientations as predictors of subsequent socio-psychological factors and ultimately attitudes and behaviours, the assumption being that value orientations are the most stable and the least likely to change over time. (Whitley et al, 2016:248). In VBN theory, the role of value and ecological worldview is emphasized (Han, 2015:166). A key component of the VBN model hinges on norm-activation theory. The norm-activation theory is based on the assumption that norms, as commonly acceptable pattern of behaviour, influence behaviour and decision-making processes (Whitley et al, 2016:249). It asserts that pro-environmental actions occur in response to personal moral norms about such actions and that these are activated in individuals who believe that environmental conditions pose threats to other people, other species, or the biosphere and that actions they initiate could avert those consequences. (Stern et al. 1999:85).

Figure 3 - The Value-Belief-Norm theory.

Source: Sustainability behaviours among college students: an application of the VBN theory (Whitley et al, 2016:248): The Value-Belief-Norm Theory.

A comparison

The Knowledge Deficit Model considers the provision of adequate knowledge enough to lead to the adoption of a certain desired behaviour and does not explore any of the socio-psychological factors that impact human behaviour. On the other hand, both the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and the Value-Belief-Norm Model (VBN) are theoretical models that show the impact that socio-psychological factors, such as beliefs, attitudes, and norms, have on human behaviour. The TPB and VBN theoretical models do not consider the factor of “knowledge” and do not explore the impact of knowledge on the adoption of a certain behaviour. All in all, little research has empirically compared the theories to identify the superiority of a particular model.

The Green Erasmus survey has drawn on the different theories attempting to provide a holistic insight on how beliefs, attitudes, norms and knowledge can affect Erasmus students’ ecological footprint, following the detailed mapping of their consumer and travel behaviour. The project overall aims at constituting a significant contribution to the scientific community as well as practitioners and policy makers.

METHODOLOGY

To understand Erasmus students' habits in relation to their environmental beliefs and attitudes, a quantitative survey was launched in spring 2021.

Research Design

The Green Erasmus survey was aimed at students who participated in an Erasmus exchange in the last three years. The focus of the survey was on consumption, travel, and daily life habits and behaviour (while at home and while on mobility) from the perspective of their beliefs and attitudes related to climate change and environmental issues. The survey investigated the criteria/motives behind the choices of Erasmus students and the relation of their actions to their beliefs. In addition, sending and hosting universities' role and impact on sustainable behaviour has been examined. For the exploration of all the aforementioned topics, the Green Erasmus survey was divided into five research areas:

A.1 At Home: habits (commuting, consumer habits) and tourism practices.

A.2 Erasmus destination: reasons for choosing the mobility destination, travelling to and from mobility destination.

A.3 On mobility: habits (commuting, consumer habits) and tourism (travelling patterns while on mobility).

A.4 University contribution to environmental awareness.

A.5 Climate transition (values, beliefs, attitudes)

The five research areas were developed to allow cross-analysis to better understand the impact of Erasmus mobility on students' habits while also investigating the role of their own value, belief system on their behaviour.

The survey used closed questions (see Annex 1) with open questions avoided given the size of the sample. These included Likert scale questions, multiple-choice questions, single choice questions (dropdown list) and masked questions (yes/no questions and ranking questions).² Some questions were drawn from previous research (Item 5, 6, 7, 15, 20, 21, 32, 33, 34, 35, 37) allowing direct comparison. Items from Chuvieco et al, (2018 - 5, 20) were used to explore students' everyday life habits while items from Rosentrater (6, 21) and Mikiki, Papadopoulou, (2017 - 7, 15) were adapted to explore students' transport preferences and the criteria behind students' choices when commuting or travelling. Finally selected items from Rosentrater et al, (2017 - 32, 34, 35) and Heeren et al. (2016 - 37) were used in the last section of the questionnaire (climate change) in order to investigate the impact of socio-psychological factors (attitudes, norms, beliefs) on students' ecological footprint.

Figure 4 - Green Erasmus research areas.

² As masked questions are defined (by limesurvey) all questions where the input of answers is predefined.

Data collection

The survey was built online using the open-source survey tool **Limesurvey**. It was disseminated by the Green Erasmus project partners for a three-month period from the 9th of March 2021 to the 16th of June 2021. The link to the survey was shared through various means including websites and social media posts, promotion through internal and external networks as well as direct emails. The communications announced the survey as an Erasmus survey, but no particular attention was drawn to sustainability issues. This was done deliberately to reduce bias. Students not interested in sustainability might not have answered the survey if the promotion explicitly mentioned the topic. The survey was anonymous, but respondents could (optional) share their email in order to participate in a prize draw for Eurail passes.

In total, 20.119 responses were collected (full and partial) with 10.797 among them being valid full responses (53,6% of total). Out of the valid 10.797 responses 3.021 were dropped as only **7.776 met the criteria for analysis** (students on Erasmus mobility for students who have participated in a physical or blended type of mobility in a period not before autumn semester of 2018).

Participants

As mentioned previously, the participants targeted for the survey were **students who had participated in an Erasmus mobility in the past three years** (from autumn semester³ of 2018 onwards) before the completion of the survey. Of those, the majority (58.6%), did their mobility between the autumn semester of 2020 and the spring semester of 2021, 27.4% between the autumn semester of 2019 and the spring semester of 2020 and finally 14.1% between the autumn semester of 2018 and the spring semester of 2019.

Participants came from over 40 different countries participating in the Erasmus mobility scheme. Germany, Spain, Italy, France, Portugal, Belgium, Poland, Turkey, Austria, and Greece are the most common countries of origin for the outgoing students (80.6% of outgoing participants' universities are based in those ten countries). Spain, Germany, France, Italy, Portugal, Poland, United Kingdom, Finland, Sweden, and Belgium are the most common destination countries for the incoming students (70.9% of participants attended a university in these ten countries during their mobility).

When it comes to their level of study, **two-thirds of the participants (66.5%) were taking a bachelor's degree at the time of mobility**, 29.8% were taking a master's degree and few participants were doing a Phd. When asked about the duration of their mobility **more than half were on mobility for a period between 5 and 6 months**. Participants undertook either a physical or blended mobility.

Out of the total number of respondents, **65.8% identified as women**, with 31.7% identified as men, 0.6% as nonbinary, 0.4% as gender nonconforming, 0.3% as genderfluid, and 0.1% as other gender. The **average year of birth** of the survey participants **was 1997**.

SENDING UNIVERSITY COUNTRY

Figure 5 - Country of the Sending University.

HOSTING UNIVERSITY COUNTRY

Figure 6 - Country of the Hosting University.

Limitations

It should be noted that although **Erasmus mobility was greatly affected by the Covid-19 crisis**, which is ongoing at the time of writing, only responses of students who had experienced a physical element to their mobility to a host country were counted. Students who had undertaken a completely virtual mobility without physical presence in the country of the host university were excluded from the analysis.

RESULTS

This section presents selected key findings of the Green Erasmus survey on the habits of Erasmus students. A mapping of participants' consumer/travel habits at home and on mobility is also presented and further analysed under the lens of their attitudes towards climate change and environmental issues. The full responses to each survey question can be found in Annex 2.

Erasmus student habits while at home and while on mobility

The Green Erasmus survey investigated **student habits** (including **consumer, travel** habits and **daily life activities**) at two distinct levels:

- while **on mobility**, and
- while **at home**.

Research findings showcase interesting patterns related to students' behaviour in the two contexts.

Consumer behaviour

Within the context of exploring their consumer behaviour and the motives behind their choices, participants were asked at first, who usually does grocery shopping (at home and on mobility). Secondly, they were questioned on the criteria behind their choices. From the findings one can see that **the level of independence when it comes to “doing the groceries” increases while students are on mobility**, with 82% stating that they are the ones who usually buy their groceries, which is a 17.2% increase from while at home. An explanation can be that the students on mobility live either with other students or in the university premises. While “at home” 20% of the students live with their caregivers/guardians who largely take over the responsibility of doing the groceries. The number of students who live with caregivers/guardians during mobility is negligible.

To gain further insight on their consumer behaviour, participants were asked to evaluate a series of items related to their consumer behaviour at home and on mobility (see questions 5 and 20 Annex I). On both occasions the most common habits are related to bringing their own bag while going shopping (71.2% of the respondents at home, and 77.4% on mobility said that they “always” bring their own bag when shopping) and turning off the lights when leaving a room (79.8% of the respondents at home, and 81.4% on mobility said that they “always” turn off the lights).

It should be noted that less popular habits, such as “I usually buy used items (clothing, books, sports equipment, etc.) ” and “I buy fair-trade products”, are showing an increase (even marginal) in popularity among students while on mobility. For example, 18% said to “always” buy used items while on mobility in comparison with the 11.5% while at home. Accordingly 9.2% state that they “always” buy fair-trade products while on mobility in comparison with 7.2% while at home. Moreover a greater effort for the reduction of energy consumption is being observed while on mobility, with the percentage of students who report to “always” turn off/unplug devices when not using them increasing from 41.3% (at home) to 49.4% (on mobility).

To understand the motives behind their consumer behaviour and their choices, students were asked which are their primary criteria for buying a product. The results show a change of criteria between the “at home” and “on mobility” responses.

MOST IMPORTANT CONSUMER CRITERIA

Figure 7 - Most important consumer criteria at home and on mobility.

As highlighted in the figure 7 there is a **considerable change in priorities when it comes to the most important consumer criteria** considered in the two contexts (at home and on mobility). **When at home, quality is stated as the most important criteria** by 45.5 % of the respondents, price closely follows at 44.4%. That balance changes significantly **on mobility** where **price emerges as the most important criterion** with an increased percentage of 59.6%, leaving quality behind at 32.7% as the second. The increasing importance of price as a criterion for buying products is possibly connected to limited financial resources during mobility. Indeed, research so far has shown that **financial issues are considered a great barrier for students when considering going on Erasmus mobility** (Souto-Otero et al, 2013, p:71). It is important to note that origin and package reusability (two sustainable criteria) **appear relatively low in students' preferences**. The percentages remain considerably low at **both at home** (6.6% and 2.2% respectively) **and on mobility** levels, even showing a marginal decrease on the mobility level (4.8% and 1.8% respectively).

Travel and commuting behaviour: Travel to and from mobility destination and daily commuting

One aspect of international student mobility that has already been discussed and explored is the ecological footprint related to the transportation choices of students when going to and returning from the mobility destination.

Research so far has indicated that **most international students are likely to travel by plane, as the aviation sector accounts for the overwhelming majority of international transportation** (Shields, 2019:596). The Green Erasmus research findings confirm this trend. The plane seems to prevail as the preferred means of transport among Erasmus students, both when they are going to (73.1%) and when they are leaving from (69.8%) the mobility destination. Its use is, by a large margin, the most prevalent among all other transport options (coach/bus, train, ship/boat, other). These numbers are also in line with recent research conducted by Eurail (in cooperation with ESN) on Erasmus students' travel behaviour. The results showed that 75% of students use planes to move to their Erasmus destination and 79% to return from their mobility (Eurail, ESN, 2020:4), drawing a similar picture with the results of the Green Erasmus survey.

Continuing on the topic of transport, students were asked about their daily commuting choices to university (home and away). Participants' responses provide some insightful findings regarding students' choices while on mobility and while at home. **Findings show that there is a considerable increase among those who choose to walk to university** (28.3% at home to 43.2% on mobility) **and a subsequent decrease in the use of public transport or a car to commute**, especially car use drops from 5.8% to 0.7%. This change cannot and should not be immediately attributed to an increased environmental awareness, as only 21.5% of the respondents said that they considered the ecological footprint of the transport when choosing transport, but it is nevertheless a good indicator of a decrease in students' ecological

footprint. Rosentrater et al, (2017)" also stated that 52% of the students (participating in their research) prefer to walk to the university campus. The authors justify this choice with the fact that most students live near the campus. Given the fact that cost/price plays an important role in students' consumer choices, it is no wonder that walking, as a free commuting choice, is preferred in the case that distance allows it.

TRANSPORT: GOING TO MOBILITY DESTINATION

Figure 8 - Going to mobility destination.

TRANSPORT: RETURNING FROM MOBILITY DESTINATION

Figure 9 - Returning from mobility destination.

DAILY COMMUTING CRITERIA

When asked to justify their transport choices and provide the motives behind them, participants highlighted three factors as the main force behind their choice: time, distance, and price. The criteria behind the choices remain almost unchanged across the two contexts (home, mobility) and are related again to the factors of time, distance, and price. This comes in line with the findings of Mikiki' and Papadopoulou's (2017) research where 360 individuals were asked about their travel mode choice criteria. Time saving was the most important criterion (39%) and money saving came close as the second most important criterion (29%).

Figure 10 - The three most important criteria behind daily commuting transport choices, at home and on mobility.

Tourism patterns

Another aspect that was explored as part of the survey was the tourism patterns of Erasmus students. Students were asked whether they travelled during the 12 months before their mobility and during the mobility, the length and destination of their trips and the means of transport they used for travelling. More than 60% reported to have travelled away from home in the 12 months before their mobility and during the period of their mobility (63.5% and 60.6% respectively).

Regarding the means of transport, there is a considerable change in preferences. **For trips at home, air travel emerged as the most popular choice with 29.6%. On the other hand, for trips during their mobility, the train emerges as the most popular choice of transportation, with 28.3%.** In this case, flying shows a decrease in popularity (22.3%) taking the third place in student preference after train and bus.

What transport methods did you use to travel to and from the destination of the trips you made?

		At home	On mobility
	Plane	29.6%	22.3%
	Train	24.7%	28.3%
	Car	24.1%	18.1%
	Coach/Bus	16.0%	24.9%
	Ship/Boat	3.1%	4.8%
	Bike	2.1%	1.2%
	Other	0.4%	0.3%
Total		100.0%	100.0%

Table 1 - Transport choices while travelling (at home and on mobility).

When further exploring the choices of those opting for plane travel it becomes clear that low cost/budget airlines are by far the most popular choice among respondents.

78.5% of students choosing aviation as means of transport, use low-cost airlines during mobility. The percentage is comparable with that of when travelling while at home (73.6%).

Given the importance stressed by students on cost/price as a factor that impacts their consumption and travelling patterns the result is not surprising. However, it is in opposition with the importance of the “quality” criterion in their purchases (1st in importance while at home and 2nd while on mobility).

It should be noted that when travelling during mobility students are more likely to take shorter trips (1-3 day) and travel in the host country or in neighbouring countries.

The overall percentage of students who choose to travel to European or non-European countries other than the country of residence and its immediate neighbouring countries is considerably lower in comparison to when travelling while at home. For example, 49.8% of Erasmus students took at least one short trip (1-3 days) in the host country, while only 9.3% chose to travel to another European country (beyond the host country and its neighbours). Those percentages stand at 47.5% and 16.7% respectively when travelling while at home. The difference in tourism patterns while on mobility and while at home can to a certain degree justify the increased use of train and bus in the first case at the expense of air travel. A similar picture has been drawn in the research of Dolnicar and Lovrentjev (2015). The findings of their survey, which was distributed to Erasmus students in Prague, showed that students tend to make shorter trips (1-3 days) and travel mostly to neighbouring countries during their Erasmus mobility.

Impact of attitudes, beliefs and awareness levels on students' behaviour: A cross-analysis

As already mentioned, research so far has shown that **ecological concern is not necessarily translated into more sustainable practices** (Chuvieco et al, 2018:1373). For this reason, students were asked a series of questions exploring their attitudes on climate transition, their awareness levels, and related actions taken. **The findings, in contrast with their actual habits, can highlight the relationship between theory and action of the respondents.**

Participants were asked about their level of concern regarding climate change. The findings indicate that **more than half of the respondents (M=1.54, 53.1%) reported to be very concerned about climate change with two fifths (M=1.41, 40.7%) reporting to be fairly concerned about the environment.** In total, 93.8% of respondents show high levels of concern.

How concerned, if at all, are you about climate change?

	N	Minimum (1=0%)	Maximum (2=100%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
Very concerned	7776	1	2	1.54	.499
Fairly concerned	7776	1	2	1.41	.492
Not very concerned	7776	1	2	1.05	.223
Not at all concerned	7776	1	2	1.01	.080
I don't know	7776	1	2	1.00	.061

Table 2 - Levels of concern on climate change.

When asked about the causes of climate change 77% believed that humans/ individuals impact climate change and 79.2% believed that individuals need to be responsible for taking action to combat climate change.

Figure 11 - The percentage of students who believe individuals impact climate change / individuals need to be responsible to take action to combat climate change.

The attitude-behaviour gap

The **findings show** that **high levels of concern on environmental issues** and **a sense of responsibility** among individuals do not always translate into action though.

Although eight out of ten participants believe that individuals are responsible for taking actions on climate change, when asked in which ways they are engaged, the responses were contradictory.

Only 4.2% have contacted the media on the issues, only 5.1% tried to directly contact a politician and only 11.1% have been part of a local community that helps. On the other hand 83.8% reported that they have changed their behaviour, 55.5% that they engaged with media working on environmental issues and 56.1% that they have signed an online petition. Those were by far the two **most popular actions taken** and although they **are showing a certain level of commitment they are also indicating some level of slacktivism**⁴. Apart from the above mentioned, a significant percentage of 32.9% have been part of a club or group dealing with environmental issues.

This pattern of gaps between the theory and the practice can be further explored in the findings related to the behaviour (consumer, travel) of the students highlighted in the previous section. For example, consumer criteria such as origin of product and sustainable packaging seem to have little impact on students' choices in comparison with criteria such as price and quality.

Students on mobility pay much more attention to the price of a product (59.6%) than the origin (4.8%) or package reusability (1.8%) when buying, regardless of the fact that more than 9 out of 10 report to be at least fairly concerned about the environment. Even among those students that report to be "Very concerned" about climate change the consumer criteria doesn't show any significant variation of those of the total sample (as it can be seen on Table 3) and barriers related to students' budget affect their choices regardless of their intentions.

⁴ working to achieve political or social change by using the internet to carry out actions that are thought to require little effort or time. (<https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/slacktivism>)

Very concerned* consumer criteria on mobility crosstabulation

		Brand	Origin	Package reusability	Price	Quality	Total
Very concerned	% within 'very concerned'	0.8%	6.3%	2.8%	56.3%	33.7%	100.0%
Total	% within total	1.1%	4.8%	1.8%	59.6%	32.7%	100.0%

Table 3 - Most important consumer criteria among students who are "Very Concerned" about climate change.

Accordingly, the biggest percentage of Erasmus students travelling to and from the mobility destination by plane prioritise price and time/distance factors. Only 5.5% (travel to mobility destination) and 6.3% (travel from the mobility destination) consider the ecological footprint of their mode of travel. Again, in this case the time/distance and cost/price are the main factors impacting their choice. It must be noted though, at this point, that **those who consider themselves "Very concerned" about climate change are less likely to use planes in comparison with those who consider themselves "Not concerned at all"**. For instance, 67.8% of those "Very concerned" use the plane when coming back from the mobility destination in comparison with the 76% of those "Not at all concerned". The respective percentages are 71.6% in comparison to 76% for when going to the mobility destination.

Norms: The impact of the immediate environment

Another aspect affecting students' sustainable behaviour is the element of norms highlighted in some of the theoretical models (see theoretical framework section, p.8). Respondents were asked to evaluate a series of items related to the level of approval of certain sustainable behaviours by their immediate environment. The results can shed a light on some of the behaviours tracked previously.

The assumption that norms, as commonly acceptable patterns of behaviour, influence behaviour and decision-making processes, as stressed in Schwartz's norm activation theory (Whitley et al, 2016:249), is largely confirmed by the results of the survey.

For example, students responding to the related questions responded that only 13.3% of the people important to them strongly agree with driving less. This might have an impact on students' transport choices (extensive use of planes) and the low impact of the criterion "ecological footprint" on their transport choices. Accordingly the responses to items 5 and 20⁵ of the survey, as mentioned in the consumer behaviour section (see p.17), highlighted that students in both cases (home, mobility) show high engagement with energy/power saving actions (I turn off the lights., I turn off/unplug electronic devices when not using). Students report, indeed, that "Conserving energy" is an action highly endorsed with 60.2% reporting that those important to them strongly agree with the statement.

5 To what extent, if at all, do you practice the habits below in your everyday life at home (5)/on mobility (20).

Levels of awareness: Knowledge and behaviour

According to the Knowledge Deficit Model, knowledge is the key component determining whether an individual behaves in a certain way or adopts a certain behaviour (Heeren et al, 2016:616). The overall percentage of students who believe that they are very or moderately informed on environmental issues exceeds 90%. Those findings are in line with the amount of those that are showing high levels of concern on climate change, as seen in the previous section.

The findings of the survey support, to some extent, the critics of the Knowledge Deficit Model which assumes that adoption of a certain behaviour is based solely on acquired knowledge. **Although nine out of ten students report to be informed on environmental**

issues and concerned about climate change once again, they seem hesitant in adopting certain behaviours (actively organise community events, engage with media working on environmental issues, be part of community clubs etc.) or give up on certain habits (extensive use of plane, use of low-cost airlines). **This is, however, a phenomenon not limited to the student population.**

It should be noted that even though information and knowledge alone might not instigate certain behaviours, they certainly have an impact. As can be seen in Table 4, when looking at the sub data for those stated to be very informed on environmental issues, in comparison with the data for the overall sample in Table 1, the findings exhibit some substantial differences.

What transport methods did you use to travel to and from the destination of the trips you made?

	At home (Very informed)	At home (Total sample)		On mobility (Very informed)	Price (Total sample)
Plane	26.9%	29.6%		20.7%	22.3%
Train	26.8%	24.7%		28.9%	28.3%
Car	23.1%	24.1%		18.9%	18.1%
Coach/Bus	16.4%	16.0%		24.3%	24.9%
Ship/Boat	3.4%	3.1%		5.4%	4.8%
Bike	2.8%	2.1%		1.5%	1.2%
Other	0.6%	0.4%		0.3%	0.3%
Total	100.0%	100.0%		100.0%	100.0%

Table 4 - Transport choices when travelling among students who are "Very Informed" on environmental issues.

Indeed "Very Informed" students are less likely to fly by plane (26.9% compared to 29.6% of the overall sample) and more likely to travel by train (26.8% compared to 24.7% of the overall sample). The differences, though, are too marginal to assume that the acquisition of knowledge directly leads to more sustainable behaviours.

When talking about the levels of information on environmental issues and its impact on students' behaviour it would be helpful to also have an insight on the source of their knowledge. As seen before, nine out of ten students reported to be at least moderately informed but what are the sources of that information?

Which are your main sources of information on environmental issues?

	N	Minimum (1=0%)	Maximum (2=100%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
News media	7776	1	2	1.29	.456
Internet	7776	1	2	1.86	.342
University	7776	1	2	1.36	.479
Friends / Family	7776	1	2	1.38	.485
Government	7776	1	2	1.22	.414
My own opinion	7776	1	2	1.33	.472
Social media	7776	1	2	1.59	.491
Other info sources	7776	1	2	1.04	.191

Table 5 - Main sources of information on environmental issues.

As can be seen in Table 5, **the Internet is by far the most common source of information for students followed by social media.** More specifically, out of total, 86.5% (M=1.86) and 59.2% (M=1.59) get their information on environmental issues from the Internet and social media respectively. On the other hand, **their university seems to play a less significant role as a source of information** with only 35.5% (M=1.36) naming university as their main source of information.

Yet, **70.9% of respondents “strongly agree” with the active promotion of environmental sustainability of their higher education institutions.** More precisely, they declare being interested to see more actions: for example, they would like to see **food waste composting** taking place on campus (57.4%), instalment of **donation points for food and clothes** (56.5%), **more sustainable food options** in campus canteens (54.1%), and an overall **ban of plastic products** (54.3%).

**CONCLUDING
DISCUSSION &
OUTLOOK**

The survey allowed a comprehensive mapping of students' behaviour and consumption patterns. For most of the consumption patterns, there are only marginal differences between home and Erasmus destinations. The few differences can be explained by the context of staying in another country, for instance, more students are living in the host university premises than in their home country. Therefore, without consciously aiming at being more sustainable, many choose more sustainable means when it comes to their daily commuting (more students choose to walk) and travelling (more students choose to travel by train). Indeed, changes can be observed in the travel patterns as most students limit their travel within their host and maybe neighbouring countries. Accordingly, the use of trains increases during mobility. Still, the vast majority choose to fly to and from the mobility destination.

Looking deeper into the results of the Green Erasmus research, it is obvious that there is a certain gap between attitudes and practice among Erasmus students when it comes to the adoption of more environmentally sustainable habits and behaviours. Although most of the students seem concerned about climate change (nine out of ten) and consider themselves informed (nine out of ten), they seem hesitant to adopt certain sustainable habits (such as conserving energy, considering their ecological footprint when choosing to buy a product or flying). **Factors like price/cost and distance constitute substantial barriers in the adoption of more sustainable behaviours. Knowledge and information, usually acquired from sources like social media, are factors that impact students' behaviour but they fail to really engage students to take action.** To a lesser degree, students receive information from sources like universities or governments.

An added value of the survey is the investigation of the socio-psychological (attitudes, beliefs etc.) factors that impact student behaviour and can lead, or not, to the adoption of certain behaviours. Based on well-known theoretical models such as the Knowledge Deficit Model, the Theory of Planned Behaviour and the Value-Belief-Norm theory, the Green Erasmus project

aims to explore students' behaviour through a more holistic approach. Socio-psychological factors (beliefs, norms) as well as levels of awareness on environmental issues are being considered in an attempt to highlight what causes Erasmus students to act in a certain way.

The results support the critics of the Knowledge Deficit Model suggesting that information on its own does not guarantee the adoption of a more sustainable behaviour. The results of the Green Erasmus survey show that **Erasmus student behaviour is multifaceted and is being impacted by a variety of factors. Those include socio-psychological factors** (as indicated by the Theory of Planned Behaviour and the Value-Belief-Norm model) **and knowledge/awareness itself** (as indicated by the Knowledge Deficit Model). As the research findings indicate, those factors have significant impact on the development of certain behaviours. For instance, **the students very concerned about the environment appear to make more sustainable choices, however the differences within the groups are not very significant.** When it comes to external barriers hindering the adoption of a more sustainable lifestyle, the cost/price emerges again as a big limitation when it comes to consumer and travel choices and greatly affects students' decisions. Those factors seem to greatly impact students' decisions (regardless of their initial attitudes on the environment) and possibly hinder the development of more sustainable habits. It can be concluded, that in spite of the amount of information on sustainability students get from social and other media as well as their universities (home or host), the behaviour of students going for an Erasmus semester in another country does not show any significant alteration. As mentioned previously, the few **changes** that can be **observed between the home and the host country are very likely connected to other external factors**, such as living on campus and therefore preferring walking instead of any other transport mode.

While **students participate in actions against climate change, their choices, at times, appear to be in contradiction with this engagement.**

This phenomenon is very often observed in the general population, but it shows that stakeholders such as universities, student organisations and also the EU need to integrate more sustainable requirements and actions in their policies, proceed with more systematic changes and, more importantly, communicate them.

Yet, respondents express concerns on environmental issues and request more initiatives and actions by their Higher Education Institutions. From that perspective, the right initiatives could possibly result in a shift in behaviour.

Such actions in combination with a possible revision in the funding policies of the Erasmus program (especially when it comes to student transportation and subsistence) and a more centrally coordinated communication strategy among European Higher Education Institutions could lead to better outcomes in the future when it comes to the ecological footprint of Erasmus students.

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**ANNEX I:
THE GREEN ERASMUS
QUESTIONNAIRE**

A1 At home: Habits (commuting, consumer habits) and tourism practices.

Consumer and sustainable habits

Q1. Who do you live with at home?

- Caregivers/Guardians
- Flatmates/partner
- With other university students
- Alone
- Other

Q2. Who usually does the shopping (groceries) while at home?

- Me
- Parents/family
- Flatmates/partner
- Other

Q3. Which of the following options describes your eating habits whilst at university? Choose the most frequent option.

- I eat homemade meals (cooked by me or the people I live with)
- I get takeaways/delivered foods
- I go to my university accommodation's canteen
- I eat out (at cafes, restaurants etc.)
- Other

Q4. What are your main criteria for buying products (food, clothes, furniture)? Put the following items in order from most to least important (where 1 is the most important and 5 is the least important).

- Quality
- Price
- Brand
- Origin
- Other

Q5. To what extent, if at all, do you practice in the habits below in your everyday life while at home?¹

	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
I usually bring my own bag when I go shopping.	<input type="radio"/>				
I separate rubbish by type (glass, plastics, paper, organic or other).	<input type="radio"/>				
I try to avoid printing documents.	<input type="radio"/>				
I try to save water at home (by showering instead of bathing, using water economisers for taps and showerheads, not keeping the tap running while brushing teeth, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>				
I prefer products with recyclable or reusable packaging.	<input type="radio"/>				
I usually buy used items (clothing, books, sports equipment, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>				
I tend to reuse plastic bottles.	<input type="radio"/>				
I buy products labelled as organic.	<input type="radio"/>				
I use eco-friendly products for cleaning and self-care.	<input type="radio"/>				
I buy fair-trade products (products that ensure better trade and social conditions for producers).	<input type="radio"/>				
I try to reuse things that can be useful for me or for others (furniture, packaging, sports equipment, books, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>				
I turn the lights off when leaving a room.	<input type="radio"/>				
I turn off/unplug electronic devices when not using them.	<input type="radio"/>				

Daily commuting

Q6. How do you usually get to university on a daily basis? Select the mode that makes up the longest part of your journey.²

- Public transport
- Walking
- Driving your own car/scooter (fuel)
- Driving a shared car/scooter (electric)
- Bike
- Other
- None of these

Q7. Why do you choose to travel this way? Choose the three (max.) most important factors.³

- Time taken to complete the journey
- Cost/price relation
- Because my friends travel this way
- Interest in comfort
- Sense of security
- Habit
- Convenience
- Flexibility/freedom
- Ecological footprint of the mode of travel
- No other choice

Tourism

Q8. Have you travelled away from home in the last 12 months before your mobility?

- Yes
- No

Q9. How often, if at all, did you go on short (1-3 nights) or long (4 nights or more) trips away from home in the last 12 months before your mobility? And where were they to?

(If you didn't travel at all before your mobility, please skip to question 11.)

	Short Trip (1-3 nights)	Long Trip (4 nights or more)
Country of residence	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)
Neighbouring country	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)
Other European* country (not country of residence or neighbouring)	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)
Other non-European country (not country of residence or neighbouring)	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)

* including the UK.

Q10. In general, what transport methods did you use to travel to and from the destination of the trips you made?

- Plane
- Car
- Coach/bus
- Bike
- Train
- Ship/boat
- Other

Q11. You said you travelled by plane for your trips, which kind of airline did you most frequently choose to fly with?

- Low cost/budget airline
- Regular (national carrier etc.)
- Not sure

A2 Erasmus destination: Reasons for choosing the mobility destination, travelling to and from mobility destination.

Mobility Destination Choice

Q12. How important were the following elements in choosing a mobility destination?

Please choose the three most important elements.

- Teaching quality of the hosting institution
- Reputation of the hosting institution
- Matching courses which can be recognised by my home institution
- Living costs in the destination country/city
- Location of the mobility destination and distance from residence country
- Interest in the culture of the mobility destination
- Ability to speak the language of the mobility destination
- Friends/family in the destination country/city
- Aspirations for a career in the destination country/city
- Other

Q13. & Q14. What kind of transport did you use for travelling to and from the mobility destination?

Select the mode that forms the biggest part of the journey.

Travelling to mobility destination (from home)

Select one: ▼
Plane
Car
Coach/Bus
Train
Ship/Boat
Other

Travelling from mobility destination (to home)

If you are still on mobility, indicate the mode of transport you will most likely choose to return home.

Select one: ▼
Plane
Car
Coach/Bus
Train
Ship/Boat
Other

Q15. What are the most important reasons for choosing this specific mode of transport? Select the most important factor in each case.⁴

	Travelling to mobility destination	Travelling from mobility destination
Time taken to complete the journey	0	0
Cost/Price	0	0
Because my friends travel this way	0	0
Interest in comfort	0	0
Sense of security	0	0
Habit	0	0
Convenience	0	0
Flexibility/freedom	0	0
Ecological footprint of the mode of travel	0	0
No other choice	0	0

A3 On mobility: Habits (commuting, consumer habits) and tourism (travelling patterns while on mobility).

Please answer the following questions referring to the time spent studying at your Erasmus+ host institution within the framework of your Erasmus+ mobility scheme.

Consumer and Sustainable Habits

Q16. During your Erasmus+ mobility, who did/do you live with?

- Caregivers/Guardians
- Flatmates/partner
- University students (in a university accommodation)
- Alone
- Other (please specify)

Q17. During your Erasmus+ mobility, who usually did/does the shopping (groceries)?

- Me
- Parents/family
- Flatmates/partner
- Other (please specify)

Q18. Which of the following options best describes/described your eating habits whilst on your Erasmus+ mobility? Choose the most frequent option.

- I eat homemade meals (cooked by me or people I live with)
- I get takeaways/delivered foods
- I go to my university accommodation's canteen
- I eat out (at cafes, restaurants etc.)
- Other (please specify)

Q19. What are your main criteria for buying products (food, clothes, furniture, etc.) whilst on your Erasmus+ mobility? Put the criteria in order (1-5) from most to least important.

- Quality
- Price
- Brand
- Origin
- Other

Q20. Please state how often, if at all, you practice/practiced the habits below in your everyday life whilst on Erasmus+ mobility.⁵

	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Frequently	Always
I usually bring my own bag when I go shopping.	<input type="radio"/>				
I separate rubbish by type (glass, plastics, paper, organic or other).	<input type="radio"/>				
I try to avoid printing documents.	<input type="radio"/>				
I try to save water at home (by showering instead of bathing, using water economisers for taps and showerheads, not keeping the tap running while brushing teeth, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>				
I prefer products with recyclable or reusable packaging.	<input type="radio"/>				
I usually buy used items (clothing, books, sports equipment, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>				
I tend to reuse plastic bottles.	<input type="radio"/>				
I buy products labelled as organic.	<input type="radio"/>				
I use eco-friendly products for cleaning and self-care.	<input type="radio"/>				
I buy fair-trade products (products that ensure better trade and social conditions for producers).	<input type="radio"/>				
I try to reuse things that can be useful for me or for others (furniture, packaging, sports equipment, books, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>				
I turn the lights off when leaving a room.	<input type="radio"/>				
I turn off/unplug electronic devices when not using them.	<input type="radio"/>				

Daily commuting

Q21. How do/did you usually get to university on a daily basis while on your Erasmus+ mobility? Select the mode that makes up the longest part of your journey.⁶

- Public transport
- Walking
- Driving your own car/scooter (fuel)
- Driving a shared car/scooter (electric)
- Bike
- Other
- None of these

Tourism

Q22. Why do/did you choose that option? Choose the three (max.) most important factors.

- Time taken to complete the journey
- Cost/price relation
- Because my friends travel this way
- Interest in comfort
- Sense of security
- Habit
- Convenience
- Flexibility/Freedom
- Ecological footprint of the mode
- No other choice

Q23. Have you travelled away from home during the period of your mobility?

- Yes
- No

Q24. How often, if at all, did you go on short (1-3 nights) or long (4 nights or more) trips away from home during the period of your Erasmus+ mobility (or in the period right before the beginning or the end of your mobility)? And where did you go?

If you haven't travelled at all, please skip to question 25.

	Short Trip (1-3 nights)	Long Trip (4 nights or more)
Country of residence	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)
Neighbouring country	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)
Other European* country (not country of residence or neighbouring)	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)
Other non-European country (not country of residence or neighbouring)	never-10 (as dropdown list)	never-10 (as dropdown list)

* including the UK.

Q25. In general, what transport methods did you use to travel to and from the destination of the trips you made?

- Plane
- Car
- Coach/bus
- Bike
- Train
- Ship/boat
- Other

Q26. You said you travelled by plane for your trips. Which kind of airline did you most frequently choose to fly with?

- Low cost/budget airline
- Regular (national carrier etc.)
- Not sure

A4 University contribution to environmental awareness.

Q27. How informed do you consider yourself to be on environmental issues?

- Very informed
- Moderately informed
- Slightly informed
- Not informed at all

Q28. Which are your main sources of information on environmental issues? Choose the three most important ones.

- News outlets
- The internet
- University
- Friends/family
- Governmental reports
- My own opinions or experiences
- Social media
- Other

Q29. & Q30. Are there any awareness raising or active engagement initiatives/actions on environmental sustainability issues within your home or hosting institution/university that you are aware of?

	Home Institution	Hosting Institution
Communication campaigns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
On campus seminars and workshops	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online seminars and workshops	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conferences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Projects with active student participation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Student clubs/groups addressing environmental issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
None	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't know	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q31. To what extent, if at all, would you say that you personally agree with the following statements:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Environmental sustainability is something which universities should actively incorporate and promote.	<input type="radio"/>				
Environmental sustainability is something which all university courses should actively incorporate and promote.	<input type="radio"/>				
Environmental sustainability is something that all course tutors should be required to incorporate within their teaching.	<input type="radio"/>				
Environmental sustainability is something which I would like to learn more about.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q32. What actions are you aware of that universities (home or host) are already implementing and what actions do you think they should start to implement to develop a more sustainable mode of operation?⁷

	Actions being implemented	Actions not implemented yet but should be implemented	Actions not being implemented but I am not interested in seeing such actions being implemented
Use of more energy from renewable sources (including generating their own renewable energy)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provision of more access to on-campus recycling for students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Use of recycled products (paper, plastic etc.) within the university premises	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provision of more sustainable food options through university catering	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Banning the use of one-time-use plastic products (bottles, bags etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provision of possibilities for on-campus composting of food waste	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Popularisation of donation points for food/clothing etc. and making it attractive to students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Development of an internal used books selling system (outside of social media usage)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
No related actions are being implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not interested in seeing such actions being implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A5 Climate Transition.

Beliefs and Attitudes

Q33. How concerned, if at all, are you about climate change?⁸

- Very concerned
- Fairly concerned
- Not very concerned
- Not at all concerned
- I don't know

Q34. What is, in your opinion, causing climate change?⁹

- Humans
- Natural processes
- Other
- Climate change is not happening

Q35. Who, if anybody, should take responsibility for making changes to combat climate change? Select all that apply.¹⁰

- Companies
- Individuals
- Governments
- Communities
- Universities
- Non-profit organisations

**Q36. Which of the following actions have you taken for combating climate change?
Please pick all that apply.**

	At home	On mobility
Signed a petition (online or in person/on paper)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Contacted a politician directly	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gone on a protest or demonstration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Spoken to an influential person	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Joined an organisation linked to climate change (e.g. became a member)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Donated money to an organisation linked to climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Contacted radio or TV channels, or newspapers about issues linked to climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organised an event in my community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Changed my own behaviour e.g. by choosing reusable products, saving energy, changing what I eat	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Engaged with media outlets linked to climate change e.g. read news articles, social media posts, watched YouTube videos, watched nature documentaries	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Posted content related to climate change on my social media accounts/channels	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Been part of a club or group that addresses climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Been part of a club or group that helps my local community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
None of these	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Norms

Q37. Most people who are important to me (including family, friends, peers etc.) would approve of ...¹¹

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
... reusing/recycling	<input type="radio"/>				
... conserving energy	<input type="radio"/>				
... using a reusable bottle	<input type="radio"/>				
... using stairs instead of lifts or escalators	<input type="radio"/>				
... eating organic/local food	<input type="radio"/>				
... driving less	<input type="radio"/>				
... buying recycled/second hand clothes	<input type="radio"/>				

Socio-demographic items

Educational background

Q38. Which was your level of study during your stay abroad?

- Bachelor or equivalent
- Master or equivalent
- Doctorate (PhD) or equivalent
- Internship
- Other

Q39. In which of these disciplines does your study programme fit best?

- ECONOMIC AND BUSINESS SCIENCES**
(Business studies, Management sciences, Economics, Finance)
- HUMANITIES**
(Humanities, Languages, Philological sciences, Education, Art)
- SOCIAL SCIENCES**
(Political sciences, Law, Sociology, Psychology, Geography, Communication and Information sciences)
- ENGINEERING**
(Engineering, Technology, Computer Science, Architecture, Urban and Regional Planning)
- NATURAL SCIENCES**
(Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Biology, Geology, Environmental Sciences)
- MEDICAL SCIENCES**
(Medical Sciences)
- TOURISM STUDIES**
- OTHER**

Q40. Please choose the country of your **SENDING** university from the list.

Dropdown list:

Mobility Experience

Q41. Mobility Type

If you did more than 1 mobility, which was your latest long-term mobility experience?

- Erasmus+ for studies
- Erasmus+ for traineeship
- Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree

Q42. Duration of the mobility

- less than 1 month
- 1 month
- 2 months
- 3 months
- 4 months
- 5 months
- 6 months
- 7 months
- 8 months
- 9 months
- 10 months
- 11 months
- 12 months

Q43. Please choose the semester(s) during which you had your last mobility:

- Autumn 2018 (August to January)
- Spring 2019 (February to July)
- Autumn 2019 (August to January)
- Spring 2020 (February to July)
- Autumn 2020 (August to January)
- Spring 2021 (February to July)

Q44. How did your mobility take place?

- Physically
- Blended (combination of virtual and physical learning activities)
- Virtually

Q45. Please choose the country of your HOSTING university/organisation from the list.

Dropdown list:

Demographics

Q46. Are you..

- A woman
- A man
- Non-binary
- Gender non-conforming
- Gender fluid
- Other
- Prefer not to disclose

Q47. What year were you born?

Dropdown list:

Q48. What is your nationality?

Dropdown list:

Q49. What is your country of residence?

Dropdown list:

Q50. How would you describe the area where you grew up?

- City or urban area
- Town or suburban area
- Rural area
- Prefer not to disclose

Q51. When you were under the age of 18, would you consider your family household income to be:

- Below average
- Slightly below average
- Average
- Slightly above average
- Above average
- Prefer not to disclose

Q52. Did any of your parents or guardians attend university?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know
- Prefer not to disclose

Q53. Do you consider yourself to have a specific learning disability, other disability, impairment or long-term health condition? Please pick one.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know
- Prefer not to say

[1] Adapted from “Chuvienco, E.; Burgui-Burgui, M.; Da Silva, E.V.; Hussein, K.; Alkaabi, K. (2018) Factors Affecting Environmental Sustainability Habits of University Students: Intercomparison Analysis in Three Countries (Spain, Brazil and UAE). *J. Clean. Prod.*, 198, 1372–1380.”

[2] Adapted from “Rosentrater, K. A., & Burke, B. R. (2017). University Students and Sustainability. Part 1: Attitudes, Perceptions, and Habits. *Journal of Sustainability Education*, 16, 2151-7452.”

[3] Adapted from “F. Mikiki, P. Papadopoulou. (2017). Tackling mobility environmental impacts through the promotion of student active travel.”

[4] Adapted from “F. Mikiki, P. Papadopoulou. (2017). Tackling mobility environmental impacts through the promotion of student active travel.”

[5] Adapted from “Chuvienco, E.; Burgui-Burgui, M.; Da Silva, E.V.; Hussein, K.; Alkaabi, K. (2018) Factors Affecting Environmental Sustainability Habits of University Students: Intercomparison Analysis in Three Countries (Spain, Brazil and UAE). *J. Clean. Prod.*, 198, 1372–1380.”

[6] Adapted from “Rosentrater, K. A., & Burke, B. R. (2017). University Students and Sustainability. Part 1: Attitudes, Perceptions, and Habits. *Journal of Sustainability Education*, 16, 2151-7452.”

[7] Adapted from “Rosentrater, K. A., & Burke, B. R. (2017). University Students and Sustainability. Part 1: Attitudes, Perceptions, and Habits. *Journal of Sustainability Education*, 16, 2151-7452.”

[8] <https://sustainability.nus.org.uk/our-research/our-research-reports/energy-and-climate-change/climate-change-tracker>

[9] Adapted from “Rosentrater, K. A., & Burke, B. R. (2017). University Students and Sustainability. Part 1: Attitudes, Perceptions, and Habits. *Journal of Sustainability Education*, 16, 2151-7452.”

[10] Adapted from “Rosentrater, K. A., & Burke, B. R. (2017). University Students and Sustainability. Part 1: Attitudes, Perceptions, and Habits. *Journal of Sustainability Education*, 16, 2151-7452.”

[11] Adapted from “Heeren, A. J., Singh, A. S., Zwickle, A., Koontz, T. M., Slagle, K. M., & McCreery, A. C. (2016). Is sustainability knowledge half the battle?. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*.”

**ANNEX II:
DETAILED SURVEY
RESULTS (TABLES)**

A1, A3: AT HOME VS ON MOBILITY: Habits (Commuting, Consumer Habits) and Tourism Practices

Who do you live with?

Q1. Who do you live with at home? &
Q16. Thinking about your Erasmus mobility, who did/do you live with?

		At Home (Q1)	On mobility (Q16)
	Caregivers/guardians	20.6%	0.7%
	Flatmates/partner	44.3%	49.7%
	University Accommodation	17.9%	38.0%
	Alone	12.0%	9.9%
	Other:	5.2%	1.6%
Total		100.0%	100%

Who does the groceries?

Q2. Who usually does the shopping (groceries) while at home? &
Q17. Thinking about your Erasmus mobility who usually did/does the shopping (groceries)?

		At Home (Q2)	On mobility (Q17)
	Me	64.8%	82.0%
	Caregivers/guardians	16.9%	0.9%
	Flatmates/partner	14.8%	16.3%
	Other:	3.5%	0.9%
Total		100.0%	100%

Eating Preferences

Q3. Which of the following options describes your eating habits whilst at University? Choose the most frequent option. &

Q18. Which of the following options best describes/described your eating habits whilst on your Erasmus mobility? Choose the most frequent option.

		At Home (Q3)	On mobility (Q18)
I eat	Homemade meals	80.3%	81.5%
	Takeaway/Delivery food	3.3%	3.9%
	At the University canteen	13.0%	9.3%
	Out (cafes, restaurants)	2.7%	4.8%
	Other	0.6%	0.5%
Total		100.0%	100%

Consumer Criteria

Q4. What are your main criteria for buying a product (food, clothes, furniture)? Put the following items in order from most to least important (where 1 is the most important and 5 the least important). Please rank all items. &

Q19. What are your main criteria for buying a product (food, clothes, furniture) whilst on Erasmus mobility? Put the criteria in order (1-5) from most to least important. Please rank all items.

		At Home (Q4)	On mobility (Q19)
First ranked criterion	Brand	1.3%	1.1%
	Origin	6.6%	4.8%
	Package reusability	2.2%	1.8%
	Price	44.4%	59.6%
	Quality	45.5%	32.7%
Total		100.0%	100%

Sustainable Habits

Q5. To what extent, if at all, do you practice the habits below in your everyday life while at home? &

Q20. Please state how often, if at all, you practice/practiced the habits below in your everyday life whilst on Erasmus mobility.

		At Home (Q5)	On mobility (Q20)
I always	I usually bring my own bag when I go shopping.	71.2%	77.4%
	I separate garbage by type (glass, plastics, paper, organic or other).	63.9%	53.9%
	I try to avoid printing documents.	31.2%	48.6%
	I try to save water at home (by showering instead of bathing, faucets economisers, keep the tap not running while brushing teeth, etc.).	40.0%	48.8%
	I prefer products with recyclable or reusable packaging.	39.3%	33.0%
	I usually buy used items (clothing, books, sports equipment, etc.).	11.5%	18.0%
	I tend to reuse plastic bottles.	44.0%	49.7%
	I buy products labelled as organic.	11.3%	11.4%
	I use eco-friendly products for cleaning and self-care.	13.7%	13.1%
	I buy fair-trade products (products that ensure better trade and social conditions for producers).	7.2%	9.2%
	I try to reuse things that can be useful for me or for others (furniture, packaging, sports equipment, books, etc.).	40.5%	41.0%
	I turn the lights off when leaving a room.	79.8%	81.4%
I turn off/unplug electronic devices when not using them.	41.3%	49.4%	
Total		190.9%	234.3%

Daily Commuting

Q6. How do you usually get to university on a daily basis?
Select the mode that forms the most part of the journey. &

Q21. How do/did you usually get to university on a daily basis while on Erasmus mobility? Select the mode that forms the most part of the journey.

		At Home (Q6)	On mobility (Q21)
	Bike	20.3%	16.8%
	Driving a shared car/ scooter (electric)	0.5%	0.4%
	Driving your own car/ scooter (fuel)	5.8%	0.7%
	Other	0.3%	0.9%
	Public transport	44.8%	38.0%
	Walking	28.3%	43.2%
Total		100.0%	100%

Q7. Why do you choose this option? Choose the three (max.) most important factors. &
Q22. Why do/did you choose that option? Choose the three (max.) most important factors.

		At Home (Q7)	On mobility (Q22)
Criteria Daily commuting	Time taken to complete the journey	47.2%	50.2%
	Cost/Price	49.1%	42.4%
	Friends choice	6.6%	12.9%
	Comfort	11.7%	9.6%
	Security	3.5%	3.0%
	Habit	27.7%	15.9%
	Convenience	37.9%	33.4%
	Flexibility	40.6%	33.2%
	Ecological footprint	33.0%	21.5%
	Because of distance	47.0%	46.6%
	No other choice	6.2%	6.0%
Total		310.6%	274.8%

Tourism

Q8. Have you travelled away from home in the last 12 months before your mobility? &
Q23. Have you travelled away from home during the period of your Erasmus mobility?

		At Home (Q6)	On mobility (Q21)
Travel	Yes	63.5%	60.6%
	No	36.5%	39.4%
Total		100.0%	100%

Q9. How often and where did you go on short (1-3 nights) or long (4 nights or more) trips away from home in the last 12 months before your mobility? And where were they to?

		Residence Country	
		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	21.9%	39.4%
	2	24.0%	26.4%
	3	22.1%	13.1%
	4	9.3%	6.5%
	5	8.7%	5.3%
	6	3.8%	2.9%
	7	1.6%	1.9%
	8	1.5%	0.8%
	9	0.6%	0.3%
	10	6.5%	3.3%
	Total ⁶	3690	2901
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

		Neighbouring Country	
		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	51.5%	58.5%
	2	26.4%	22.2%
	3	12.4%	8.0%
	4	3.9%	3.8%
	5	2.2%	2.6%
	6	1.1%	1.1%
	7	0.7%	1.5%
	8	0.6%	0.6%
	9	0.1%	0.3%
	10	1.0%	1.8%
	Total	2019	1893
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

⁶ Out of a total 7776 responses.

		Other European ⁷ Country	
		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	52.4%	57.2%
	2	23.2%	22.4%
	3	13.7%	8.4%
	4	4.6%	4.0%
	5	2.2%	2.5%
	6	1.5%	1.3%
	7	0.8%	1.4%
	8	0.4%	0.4%
	9	0.3%	0.5%
	10	0.9%	1.8%
	Total	1295	2364
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

		Other Non-European Country	
		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	60.9%	73.5%
	2	10.8%	12.1%
	3	11.1%	3.9%
	4	5.4%	1.2%
	5	3.9%	1.7%
	6	2.2%	0.6%
	7	1.1%	1.3%
	8	1.1%	0.5%
	9	0.4%	0.5%
	10	3.2%	4.7%
	Total	279	1042
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

⁷ By European country we are referring to Europe on geographic terms, thus including all countries belonging to the continent of Europe and not only EU countries.

Q 24 How often did you go on short (1-3 nights) or long (4 nights or more) trips away from home during the period of your Erasmus+ mobility (or in the period right before the beginning or the end of your mobility)? And where did you go?

Country of mobility (residence)

		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	23.9%	49.3%
	2	23.0%	25.8%
	3	20.7%	10.0%
	4	11.1%	5.3%
	5	9.2%	4.2%
	6	3.8%	1.6%
	7	2.1%	1.2%
	8	1.4%	0.6%
	9	0.5%	0.5%
	10	4.3%	1.5%
	Total	3873	1963
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

Neighbouring Country

		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	48.5%	59.9%
	2	24.7%	18.8%
	3	15.7%	7.9%
	4	4.6%	5.5%
	5	3.1%	3.7%
	6	1.5%	1.1%
	7	0.4%	0.8%
	8	0.5%	0.8%
	9	0.3%	0.6%
	10	0.8%	0.8%
	Total	1690	964
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

Home Country

		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	51.0%	65.1%
	2	20.7%	20.3%
	3	14.3%	5.6%
	4	4.6%	2.3%
	5	2.5%	1.2%
	6	2.4%	0.8%
	7	0.8%	0.6%
	8	0.5%	0.3%
	9	0.5%	0.5%
	10	2.7%	3.0%
	Total	830	1545
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

Other European Country

		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	48.7%	56.9%
	2	22.1%	17.3%
	3	16.0%	8.5%
	4	5.3%	6.0%
	5	2.8%	3.8%
	6	2.6%	2.4%
	7	0.6%	1.6%
	8	0.4%	0.4%
	9	0.1%	0.5%
	10	1.4%	2.5%
	Total	723	761
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

Other Non-European country

		Short trip	Long trip
Valid	1	63.1%	72.6%
	2	10.7%	10.2%
	3	15.4%	4.9%
	4	5.4%	4.9%
	5	2.0%	1.5%
	6	-	-
	7	0.7%	1.5%
	8	0.7%	1.1%
	9	0.7%	1.5%
	10	1.3%	1.9%
	Total	149	266
	Total%	100.0%	100.0%

Q10. In general, what transport methods did you use to travel to and from the destination of the trips you made? (At home) &

Q25. In general, what transport methods did you use to travel to and from the destination of the trips you made? (On mobility)

		At Home (Q10)	On mobility (Q25)
	Plane	29.6%	22.3%
	Car	24.1%	18.1%
	Coach/Bus	16.0%	24.9%
	Bike	2.1%	1.2%
	Train	24.7%	28.3%
	Ship/Boat	3.1%	4.8%
	Other	0.4%	0.3%
Total		100.0%	100%

Q11. You said you travelled by plane for your trips, which kind of airline did you most frequently choose to fly with? (At home) &

Q26. You said you travelled by plane for your trips.
Which kind of airline you most frequently choose to fly with? (On mobility)

		At Home (Q11)	On mobility (Q26)
	Low cost	73.6%	78.5%
	Regular	22.3%	18.7%
	Not sure	4.1%	2.9%
Total		100.0%	100.0%

A2 Erasmus Destination: Reasons for choosing the Mobility Destination, Travelling to and from Mobility Destination.

Q12. How important were the following elements in choosing a mobility destination?
Please choose the three most important elements.

		On mobility (Q26)
Criteria for choosing mobility destination	Teaching quality	42.4%
	Reputation	29.4%
	Matching courses	51.7%
	Living costs in destination	35.6%
	Location/distance from home	26.9%
	Interest in culture of host country	63.9%
	Ability to speak language of mobility destination	43.3%
	Friends/family in mobility destination	5.4%
	Aspirations for career in mobility destination	18.3%
	Other	6.7%
Total		323.6%

Q13. What kind of transport did you use for travelling (from home) to the mobility destination?
Select the mode that forms the biggest part of the journey &

Q14. What kind of transport did you use for travelling from the mobility destination (back home)? Select the mode that forms the biggest part of the journey.

		Going to mobility destination (Q13)	Returning from mobility destination (Q14)
Valid	Car	8.9%	8.9%
	Coach/Bus	5.1%	5.7%
	Other	0.2%	0.6%
	Plane	73.1%	69.8%
	Ship/Boat	0.7%	0.8%
	Train	11.9%	14.1%
	Total	100.0%	100.0%

Q15. What are the most important reasons for choosing this specific mode of transport? Select the most important factor in each case.

		To mobility destination	From mobility destination
Valid	Because my friends travel this way	1.6%	2.1%
	Because of distance	24.4%	23.2%
	Convenience	7.3%	7.2%
	Cost/price relation	18.2%	19.6%
	Ecological footprint of the mode	5.5%	6.3%
	Flexibility/Freedom	3.8%	4.5%
	Habit	0.9%	1.0%
	Interest in comfort	3.4%	3.0%
	No other choice	7.5%	8.8%
	Sense of security	1.7%	1.5%
	Time taken to complete the journey	25.8%	22.7%
	Total	100.0%	100.0%

A4 University Contribution to Environmental Awareness

Q27. How informed do you consider yourself to be on environmental issues?

		Percent
Levels of awareness	Very Informed	30.6%
	Moderately informed	59.5%
	Slightly informed	9.5%
	Not at all informed	0.4%
Total		100.0%

Q28. Which are your main sources of information on environmental issues? Choose the three more important ones.

		Percent
Source of information	Newsmedia	29.5%
	Internet	86.5%
	University	35.5%
	Friends/Family	37.7%
	Government	22.0%
	My own opinion	33.5%
	Social media	59.2%
	Other information sources	3.8%
Total		100.0%

Q29. Are there any awareness raising or active engagement initiatives/actions on environmental sustainability issues within your home institution/university that you are aware of? &

Q30. Are there any awareness raising or active engagement initiatives/actions on environmental sustainability issues within your hosting institution/university that you are aware of?

		Home University (Q29)	Host University (Q30)
	Communication Campaigns	14.3%	12.6%
	On campus seminars	11.7%	9.5%
	Online seminars workshops	13.8%	11.2%
	Conferences	12.5%	8.9%
	Projects with students	15.8%	13.5%
	Student clubs	15.6%	12.9%
	None	3.5%	3.6%
	I don't know	12.9%	27.9%
Total		100.0%	100.0%

Q31. To what extent, if at all, would you say that you personally agree with the following statements:

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Environmental sustainability is something which universities should actively incorporate and promote.	70.9%	21.6%	4.7%	1.2%	1.6%	100.0%
Environmental sustainability is something which all university courses should actively incorporate and promote.	41.5%	26.5%	19.9%	8.6%	3.4%	100.0%
Environmental sustainability is something that all course tutors should be required to incorporate within their teaching.	28.6%	26.1%	26.7%	13.0%	5.6%	100.0%
Environmental sustainability is something which I would like to learn more about.	56.4%	28.5%	11.2%	2.3%	1.6%	100.0%

Q32. What actions are you aware of that universities (home or host) are already implementing and what actions do you think they should start to implement to develop a more sustainable mode of operation?

	Actions being implemented	Actions not implemented yet but should be implemented	Actions not being implemented but I am not interested in seeing such actions being implemented	Total
Use of more energy from renewable sources (including generating their own renewable energy)	33.2%	55.6%	11.2%	100.0%
Provision of more access to on-campus recycling for students	50.9%	39.1%	10.0%	100.0%
Use of recycled products (paper, plastic etc.) within the university premises	45.2%	45.2%	9.6%	100.0%
Provision of more sustainable food options through university catering	31.8%	54.1%	14.1%	100.0%
Banning the use of one-time-use plastic products (bottles, bags etc.)	26.5%	54.3%	19.2%	100.0%
Provision of possibilities for on-campus composting of food waste	18.0%	57.4%	24.5%	100.0%
Popularisation of donation points for food/clothing etc. and making it attractive to students	21.9%	56.5%	21.6%	100.0%
Development of an internal used books selling system (outside of social media usage)	30.1%	52.1%	17.8%	100.0%

A5 Climate Transition

Q33. How concerned, if at all, are you about climate change?

		Percent
Concern levels on environmental issues	Very concerned	53.1%
	Fairly concerned	40.7%
	Not very concerned	5.2%
	Not at all concerned	0.6%
	I don't know	0.4%
Total		100.0%

Q34. What is, in your opinion, causing climate change?

		Percent
Cause of climate change	Humans	77.0%
	Natural processes	19.8%
	Other factor	3.0%
	Climate change is not happening	0.2%
Total		100.0%

Q35. Who, if anybody, should take responsibility for making changes to combat climate change? Select all that apply.

		Percent
Responsibility for action	Companies	90.0%
	Individuals	79.2%
	Governments	94.3%
	Communities	61.2%
	Universities	54.1%
	Non profit organisations	46.3%
Total		425.1%

Q36. Which of the following actions have you taken for combating climate change? Please pick all that apply.

		Percent
Actions taken	Signed a petition (online or in person/on paper)	56.1%
	Contacted a politician directly	5.1%
	Gone on a protest or demonstration	36.4%
	Spoken to an influential person	3.8%
	Joined an organisation linked to climate change (e.g. became a member)	8.5%
	Donated money to an organisation linked to climate change	17.7%
	Contacted radio or TV channels, or newspapers about issues linked to climate change	23.8%
	Organised an event in my community	4.2%
	Changed my own behaviour e.g. by choosing reusable products, saving energy, changing what I eat	7.0%
	Engaged with media outlets linked to climate change e.g. read news articles, social media posts, watched YouTube videos, watched nature documentaries	83.8%
	Posted content related to climate change on my social media accounts/channels	55.0%
	Been part of a club or group that addresses climate change	32.9%
	Been part of a club or group that helps my local community	11.1%
	Other	7.8%
None of these	4.0%	
Total		390.1%

Q37. Most people who are important to me (including family, friends, peers etc.) would approve of ...

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
... reusing/recycling	60.2%	29.9%	6.4%	1.7%	1.7%	100.0%
... conserving energy	53.4%	32.4%	10.5%	2.6%	1.1%	100.0%
... using a reusable bottle	55.1%	29.1%	11.5%	3.0%	1.3%	100.0%
... using stairs instead of lifts or escalators	22.5%	27.1%	31.5%	14.3%	4.6%	100.0%
... eating organic/local food	26.9%	34.2%	27.8%	9.0%	2.0%	100.0%
... driving less	13.3%	20.6%	34.9%	24.4%	6.9%	100.0%
... buying recycled/second hand clothes	14.9%	22.5%	31.1%	23.4%	8.1%	100.0%

Socio-demographic items

Q38. Which was your level of study during your stay abroad?

		Percent
Studies level	Bachelor	66.5%
	Master	29.8%
	Doctorat	0.7%
	Other	3.0%
Total		100.0%

Q39. In which of these disciplines does your study programme fit best?

		Percent
Area of studies	Economics/Business	19.0%
	Humanities	21.6%
	Social Sciences	18.7%
	Engineering	21.6%
	Natural Sciences	9.6%
	Medical Sciences	4.6%
	Tourism Studies	2.2%
	Other Studies	2.6%
	Total	100.0%

Q40. The Sending University & Q45. The Hosting University

		Percent	Percent
Valid	Afghanistan	0.0%	0.0%
	Albania	0.2%	0.0%
	Algeria	0.0%	0.0%
	Andorra	0.0%	0.0%
	Antigua and Barbuda	0.0%	0.0%
	Argentina	0.0%	0.0%
	Armenia	0.0%	0.0%
	Australia	0.1%	0.1%
	Austria	2.7%	2.7%
	Azerbaijan	0.0%	0.0%
	Bangladesh	0.0%	0.0%
	Belarus	0.1%	0.1%
	Belgium	3.5%	4.0%
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	0.1%	0.1%
	Brazil	0.0%	0.0%
	Bulgaria	0.5%	0.5%
	Canada	0.0%	0.1%
	Chile	0.0%	0.0%
	China	0.0%	0.0%
	Colombia	0.1%	0.0%
Costa Rica	0.0%	0.0%	
Côte d'Ivoire	0.0%	0.0%	
Croatia	0.9%	1.4%	

Valid	Cuba	0.0%	0.0%
	Cyprus	0.0%	0.2%
	Czech Republic	1.5%	2.9%
	Denmark	1.7%	2.2%
	Ecuador	0.0%	0.0%
	Egypt	0.1%	0.0%
	Estonia	0.3%	0.9%
	Finland	0.7%	4.7%
	France	5.2%	8.9%
	Georgia	0.2%	0.1%
	Germany	24.2%	9.4%
	Ghana	0.0%	0.0%
	Greece	2.3%	1.2%
	Grenada	0.0%	0.0%
	Hong Kong	0.0%	0.0%
	Hungary	2.0%	1.7%
	Iceland	0.1%	0.4%
	India	0.1%	0.0%
	Indonesia	0.0%	0.0%
	Iran	0.1%	0.0%
	Ireland	0.5%	1.3%
	Israel	0.0%	0.1%
	Italy	14.4%	7,5%
	Jordan	0.0%	0.0%
	Japan	0.0%	0.0%
	Kazakhstan	0.0%	0.0%
	Kosovo	0.1%	0.0%
	Latvia	0.7%	1.6%
	Lebanon	0.1%	0.0%
	Liechtenstein	0.0%	0.0%
	Lithuania	0.5%	1.1%
	Luxembourg	0.2%	0.1%
	Madagascar	0.0%	0.0%
Malta	0.2%	0.2%	
Mauritius	0.0%	0.0%	
Mexico	0.1%	0.0%	
Moldova	0.0%	0.0%	
Montenegro	0.1%	0.0%	
Morocco	0.0%	0.1%	
Natherlands	1.2%	2.8%	
Nicaragua	0.0%	0.0%	
Nigeria	0.1%	0.0%	
North Macedonia	0.0%	0.0%	
Norway	0.2%	2.9%	

Valid	Other	0.1%	0.1%
	Palestine	0.0%	0.0%
	Peru	0.0%	0.0%
	Philippines	0.1%	0.0%
	Poland	3.0%	5.1%
	Portugal	4.4%	6.0%
	Qatar	0.0%	0.0%
	Romania	2.0%	0.8%
	Russia	0.6%	0.1%
	Senegal	0.0%	0.0%
	Serbia	0.3%	0.0%
	Singapore	0.0%	0.0%
	Slovakia	0.6%	0.4%
	Slovenia	0.5%	1.0%
	South Africa	0.0%	0.0%
	South Korea	0.0%	0.1%
	Spain	17.9%	15.6%
	Sri Lanka	0.0%	0.0%
	Sudan	0.0%	0.0%
	Sweden	0.5%	4.6%
	Switzerland	0.6%	0.6%
	Thailand	0.0%	0.0%
	Togo	0.0%	0.0%
	Tunisia	0.1%	0.0%
	Turkey	3.0%	0.8%
	Ukraine	0.5%	0.0%
	United Kingdom	1.0%	5.1%
	United States of America	0.0%	0.0%
	Uzbekistan	0.1%	0.0%
	Vietnam	0.0%	0.0%
Zambia	0.0%	0.0%	
Total	100.0	100.0	

Q41. If you did more than 1 mobility, which was your latest long-term mobility experience?

	Percent
Erasmus+ for studies	100.0%

Q42. Duration of your mobility.

		Percent
Duration of mobility	Less than one month	0.6%
	One month	0.4%
	Two months	0.7%
	Three months	3.3%
	Four months	14.9%
	Five months	33.2%
	Six months	22.4%
	Seven months	1.8%
	Eight months	1.1%
	Nine months	6.3%
	Ten months	9.5%
	Eleven months	1.5%
Twelve months	4.3%	
Total		100.0%

Q43. Please choose the semester(s) during which you had your last mobility:

		Percent
Period of mobility	Autumn 2018	7.3%
	Spring 2019	6.8%
	Autumn 2019	15.2%
	Spring 2020	12.2%
	Autumn 2020	34.8%
	Spring 2021	23.8%
Total		100.0%

Q44. How did your mobility take place?

		Percent
	Physically	53.4%
	Blended	46.6%
Total		100.0%

Q46. Are you...

		Percent
Gender	Woman	65.8%
	Man	31.7%
	Non binary	0.6%
	Gender non conforming	0.4%
	Gender fluid	0.3%
	Other gender	0.1%
	Prefer not to disclose	1.2%
	Total	100.5%

Q47. What year you were born?

		Year
Mean		1997

Q48. What is your nationality?

		%				
Valid	Albanian	.3	Estonian	.3	Nicaraguan	.0
	Algerian	.0	Fijian	.0	Nigerian	.1
	American	.1	Filipino	.1	Nigerien	.0
	Angolan	.0	Finnish	.6	North Macedonian	.0
	Argentinian	.1	French	5.2	Norwegian	.2
	Armenian	.1	Georgian	.2	Other	.1
	Australian	.0	German	23.0	Pakistani	.2
	Austrian	1.2	Ghanian	.1	Palauan	.0
	Azerbaijani	.1	Greek	2.3	Palestinian	.0
	Bahamian	.0	Haitian	.0	Peruvian	.1
	Bahraini	.0	Hong Konger	.0	Polish	2.8
	Bangladeshi	.0	Hungarian	2.1	Portuguese	4.0
	Barbadian	.0	Icelandic	.0	Prefer not to disclose	.3
	Belarusian	.2	Indian	.4	Romanian	2.0
	Belgian	3.3	Indonesian	.1	Russia	.8
	Belizean	.0	Iranian	.3	Rwandan	.0
	Beninese	.0	Irish	.6	Salvadoran	.0
	Bolivian	.0	Israeli	.0	San Marinese	.0
	Bosnian Herzegovinian	.2	Italian	13.8	Senegalese	.0
	Brazilian	.5	Ivorian	.0	Serbian	.3
	British	.7	Jamaican	.0	Singaporean	.0
	Bulgaria	.3	Japanese	.1	Slovakian	.8
	Burkinese	.0	Jordanian	.0	Slovenian	.5
	Burundian	.0	Kazakhstani	.1	South African	.0
	Cameroonian	.0	Kenyan	.0	Spanish	17.9
	Canadian	.1	Kittitian or Nevisian	.0	Sri Lankan	.0
	Chilean	.1	Kosovar	.1	Sudanese	.0
	Chinese	.4	Kyrgyzstani	.0	Swedish	.4
	Colombian	.3	Latvia	.6	Swiss	.5
	Congolese (Democratic Republic of the)	.0	Lebanese	.1	Syrian	.0
	Costa Rican	.1	Libyan	.0	Taiwanese	.1
	Croatian	1.0	Lithuanian	.2	Tajik	.0
	Cuban	.0	Luxembourgish	.1	Thai	.0
	Cypriot	.1	Malagasy	.0	Togolese	.0
	Czech	1.1	Maldivian	.0	Tunisian	.1
	Danish	1.5	Maltese	.1	Turkish	3.0
	Dominican (Dominican Republic)	.0	Mauritian	.0	Turkmenistani	.0
	Dutch	.7	Mexican	.2	Ukrainian	.8
	Ecuadorian	.1	Moldovan	.2	Uzbek	.1
	Egyptian	.2	Montenegrin	.1	Venezuelan	.1
			Moroccan	.1	Vietnamese	.1
			Mosotho	.0	Zambian	.0
					Total	100.0

Q49. What is your country of residence?

		%				
Valid	Afghanistan	.0	Haiti	.0	Qatar	.0
	Albania	.2	Hong Kong	.0	Romania	1.8
	Algeria	.0	Hungary	2.0	Russia	.5
	Andorra	.0	Iceland	.1	San Marino	.0
	Angola	.0	India	.1	Senegal	.0
	Antigua and Barbuda	.0	Indonesia	.0	Serbia	.3
	Argentina	.0	Iran	.1	Singapore	.0
	Armenia	.1	Ireland	.5	Slovakia	.7
	Australia	.0	Israel	.0	Slovenia	.5
	Austria	1.6	Italy	14.4	South Korea	.0
	Azerbaijan	.1	Jordan	.0	Spain	18.3
	Bahamas	.0	Kazakhstan	.1	Sri Lanka	.0
	Bangladesh	.0	Kosovo	.1	Sudan	.0
	Barbados	.0	Kyrgyzstan	.0	Suriname	.0
	Belarus	.2	Latvia	.6	Sweden	.4
	Belgium	3.6	Lebanon	.1	Switzerland	.7
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	.3	Lesotho	.0	Syria	.0
	Brazil	.2	Liechtenstein	.0	Taiwan	.1
	Bulgaria	.2	Lithuania	.4	Thailand	.0
	Canada	.1	Luxembourg	.2	Togo	.0
	Chile	.1	Madagascar	.0	Tunisia	.1
	China	.1	Malta	.2	Turkey	3.0
	Colombia	.1	Mauritius	.0	Ukraine	.6
	Costa Rica	.0	Mexico	.1	United Arab Emirates	.0
	Côte d'Ivoire	.0	Moldova	.1	United Kingdom	1.0
	Croatia	.9	Montenegro	.1	United States of America	.1
	Cuba	.0	Morocco	.1	Uzbekistan	.1
	Cyprus	.0	Netherlands	1.0	Vietnam	.0
	Czech Republic	1.3	Nicaragua	.0	Zambia	.0
	Denmark	1.7	Nigeria	.1	Total	100.0
	Dominican Republic	.0	North Macedonia	.0		
	Ecuador	.0	Norway	.2		
	Egypt	.1	Other	.1		
Estonia	.3	Palestine	.0			
Finland	.7	Papua New Guinea	.0			
France	5.4	Peru	.0			
Georgia	.2	Philippines	.0			
Germany	23.7	Poland	2.7			
Ghana	.0	Portugal	4.5			
Greece	2.3					

Q50. How would you describe the area where you grew up in?

		Percent
Area	City	40.7%
	Town	36.5%
	Rural	22.3%
	Prefer not to say	0.5%
Total		100.0%

Q51. When you were under the age of 18, would you consider your family household income to be:

		Percent
Family Income	Below average	5.9%
	Slightly below average	12.0%
	Average	39.2%
	Slightly above average	28.7%
	Above average	10.2%
	Prefer not to disclose	4.0%
Total		100.0%

Q52. Did any of your parents or guardians attend university?

		Percent
	Yes	62.5%
	No	35.8%
	I don't know	0.7%
	Prefer not to disclose	1.0%
Total		100.0%

Q53. Do you consider yourself to have a specific learning disability, other disability, impairment or long-term health condition? Please pick one.

		Percent
Learning disability	Yes	5.2%
	No	88.4%
	I don't know	4.4%
	Prefer not to disclose	2.0%
Total		100.0%

